

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16953442

Media Technology And Youth Behaviour: A Study Of Agbani Community Of Nkanu West Local Government Area, Enugu

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the influence of media technology on youth behaviour in Agbani Community, Nkanu West Local Government Area, Enugu State. Four research questions were formulated to guide the investigation. A survey research design was adopted, with a sample size of 200 respondents representing the youth population in the community. The stratified sampling technique was employed to ensure fair representation. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and interviews, and the results were analyzed using descriptive statistics presented in tables and percentages. Findings revealed that media technology significantly impacts youth behaviour, with many respondents indicating frequent influence from media platforms. The study concluded that there is a need for proactive measures to address the negative effects of media technology on youths. Recommendations include restricting access to inappropriate online content, organizing seminars and workshops on responsible media use, and providing proper orientation to youths on the potential disadvantages of media technology.

Keywords: Media, technology, social media, youths, behaviour

INTRODUCTION

The media technology ecosystem in Sub-Saharan Africa has experienced substantial transformations in the last decade, impacting mental health results in the region (Banjoko, 2021). By mid-2022, more than half of people in some countries will have access to the internet (Internet World Stats, 2022). This means that more individuals in Sub-Saharan Africa will be able to use social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp (Deumert et al., 2019; Akinwotu, 2021). This increase in connectedness has both positive and negative consequences on mental health since people are exposed to a wide range of information and interactions that might affect their overall health (Mbiti & Weil, 2016). The expansion of mobile technology is a big part of how social media is growing in Sub-Saharan Africa. The Global Systems for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA, 2021) says that mobile technology has become the region's main way to access the internet, with more than 300 million unique mobile subscribers as of 2020. More people in the area can use social media while on the go because to the availability of smartphones and affordable data plans (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017).

This change has changed the way people talk to each other online, putting more emphasis on instant messaging and multimedia material (Chimombo & Chirwa, 2020). Even yet, this increased connectedness can make people feel more connected and supported, but it can also make them feel alone and depend on digital interactions for social connections (Banejee & Singh, 2020; Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). The rise of local content and platforms is another important aspect in the growth of social media in Sub-Saharan Africa. The increasing number of people using social media has led to a greater need for content that reflects their cultural origins and experiences (Nopanye, 2021). Because of this desire, platforms have been made just for African audiences that make it easier to share personal stories, make relationships, and

talk about things that matter to them. However, the dissemination of misinformation and false news on digital platforms can negatively impact mental health, subjecting consumers to dangerous or deceptive content that may induce worry, tension, and bewilderment (Dedeoglu, 2020).

Additionally, the impact of social media on mental health outcomes differs between urban and rural areas in Sub-Saharan Africa. In metropolitan regions, where internet connectivity is more popular and smartphone ownership is higher, social media consumption is often more intense and ubiquitous (Egunjobi & Fawole, 2020). This rise in usage can lead to more cases of cyberbullying and social media addiction because people may spend too much time online and have more bad interactions (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). On the other hand, those who live in rural areas where internet connection is limited and social media use is low may feel lonely and isolated since they don't have enough online access (Beke, 2022). In general, the growth of social media in Sub-Saharan Africa has had a wide range of effects on mental health in the area. Social media can help people connect, raise awareness about mental health concerns, and offer assistance. However, it can also make people feel more lonely, anxious, and poor self-esteem (Gonzalez et al., 2021). It is against this background, that this study investigated the impact of media technology usage on the Agbani community youths of Enugu State.

Statement of Problem

Nowadays, the media has a huge and constant impact on young people's life. It significantly influences the way in which youth create meaning and engage with the world. Media exposure, which includes television, music, video games, mobile phones, computers, and the internet, is a powerful component of children's and adolescents' social environments and has a significant impact on their behavior, attitudes, and development (Strasburger, Jordan, & Donnerstein, 2010). There are several advantages to young people having more access to media technology like smartphones, tablets, and internet-enabled gadgets, such as better communication, educational opportunities, and worldwide connectivity. However, there are also worries about the possible hazards associated with this quick technological advancement, such as exposure to improper content, cyberbullying, internet addiction, and participation in cybercrime (Livingstone & Haddon, 2009; Odumodu, 2020). There has always been public concern about the social and psychological effects of emerging technologies.

These issues are growing more and more pertinent in the Agbani community. Local reports emphasize the increasing problems caused by young people's uncontrolled use of media technology, such as the 2010 arrest of six young people engaging in cyber fraud at the Greater Tomorrow Cyber Café in Agbani. A panel of experts was assembled by the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in 2006 to evaluate the behavioral and health risks of youth media consumption in response to similar concerns. The panel emphasized the necessity of policies and educational initiatives to reduce these risks (Robinson et al., 2008). Despite ongoing interventions by government and non-governmental organizations, the negative impacts of media technology on youth, particularly in terms of deviant behavior and academic performance, remain visible in many communities, including Agbani. Given these concerns, it becomes imperative to investigate the influence of media technology on youth behavior and explore its broader social implications within the Agbani community of Nkanu West Local Government Area, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this paper is to evaluate the impact of media technology usage on the Agbani community youths. The specific objectives include:

1. To assess the extent of media technology usage among youths in Agbani Community.
2. To identify the key factors contributing to the influence of media technology on the youth in the community.
3. To examine the effects of media technology on the social life of Agbani Community.
4. To explore strategies for mitigating the negative impacts of media technology on the lives of the youth.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. To what extent is media technology used by youths in Agbani Community?

2. What factors are responsible for the influence of media technology on the youth in the community?
3. What are the effects of media technology on the social life of Agbani Community?
4. What measures can be taken to mitigate the negative impacts of media technology on the lives of the youths?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. It covers a broad area of observation, which means using a selected sample from a fraction of the population to analyze a large population at a given point in time. This research technique was used because it made it possible for the researcher to use the sample drawn to represent the different elements of the population under study.

Literature Review

Young people's lives now revolve around media technology, especially social media, which provides a vibrant forum for identity building, self-expression, and communication. Platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok, and X (previously Twitter) are very popular among young people in Nigeria, influencing their social connections and sense of self. Given that excessive use of social media has been connected to a number of psychological issues, such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem, it is critical to comprehend the extent of social media use in this demographic context in order to assess its effects on mental health (Olugbenga et al., 2022; Omolaiya, et al., 2015). Social media has become the main means of communication for today's young, and they are completely absorbed in it. Their emotional and cognitive development is greatly influenced by this engagement. Social media is linked to a number of detrimental effects on mental health, even while it gives Nigerian youth the chance to interact, exchange stories, and keep up with current events (Agbo, 2021).

According to research, youths who have greater access to and usage of media technologies, including social media, are more likely to experience problems like anxiety, depression, suicidal thoughts, and low self-esteem (Ajike & Nwakoby, 2016). Social media's direct impact on Nigerian youths' psychological health has been the subject of numerous research. Research indicates that unfettered social media use is associated with an increase in mental health concerns, which are exacerbated by exposure to toxic content and cyberbullying. Additionally, these platforms' addictive qualities have a detrimental effect on young Nigerians' academic achievement (Ajike & Nwakoby, 2016; Keles et al., 2020).

Regular use of social media can affect an adolescent's life in a number of ways, such as: Academic Performance: Overuse can have a detrimental effect on study time and lower academic achievement. - Sleep Patterns: Poorer sleep hygiene and quality are associated with increased screen usage, particularly before bed (Chen et al., 2016). Social Interactions: Although social media can improve communication abilities, it may also result in less in-person encounters (Akintola, 2021).

Social media use among young people worldwide frequently exceeds several hours per day, having both beneficial and detrimental effects. Given how quickly social media platforms are growing, it is more important than ever to comprehend how they affect the lives of young people. This study provides empirical data on media technology usage and its impact on young people's behavior, acknowledging that young people are among the most active social media users. Research like this gives parents, teachers, and mental health specialists valuable information. Developing interventions to encourage better online behaviors can be facilitated by an understanding of usage trends and patterns.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents based on age

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
18-23	126	63%
24-29	54	27%
30-35	18	9%
36 above	2	1%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 1 above shows that the highest proportion, made up of the 126 respondents (63%), falls within the age range of 18-23 years, followed by the 24-29 years age range, which constituted 54 respondents (27%). Respondents within the age range of 30-35 took the third position with 18 respondents (9%). Those of 36 and above year's age range came last with (1%).

Table 2: Percentage distribution of respondents' formal education qualification

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percentage
FSLC	0	0%
WASSE/GCE/equivalent	56	28%
Diploma /1 st Degree and above	144	72%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 indicated that respondents with diploma/1st degree and above were the highest with 144 (72), followed by respondents with WASC/GCE/Equivalent, who constituted 56 (28%), while those with first school leaving certificate (FSLC) were last with 0% indicating that there was no respondent with just FSLC.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	0	0%
Single	200	100%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The above shows that the segment of the population used for the study was the single youths.

Table 4: Responses to the extent to which media technology is used by the youths in Agbani.

Degree of media technology	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	90	45%
High	56	28%
Low	36	18%
Very low	18	9%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4 indicates that the highest proportion of respondents, 90 (45%), rated the use of media technology by the youths in the community very high. This was followed by (56) 28% respondents who rated the degree of usage "high". Additionally, 36 respondents (18%) considered the level of media technology usage to be low, while the remaining 18 respondents (9%) rated it as very low.

Table 5: Responses to the factors responsible for the effect of media technology in the community

Factors responsible for the effect of media technology	Frequency	Percentage
Improper orientation of the youths about media disadvantage	145	72.5%
Low cost of media technology	35	17.5%
Easy access to existing technology	20	10%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 5 indicates that the highest proportion of 145 respondents (72.5%) identified improper orientation of the youths about media disadvantages as the major factor responsible for the influence of media technology. This was followed by 35 respondents (17.5%) who cited the low cost of media technology. Additionally, 20 respondents (10%) attributed the influence to easy access to existing technology.

Table 6: Responses to how media technology influenced the youth's behavior in Agbani Community

How has youth behavior been influenced by media technology	Frequency	Percentage
Less time for academic work	100	50%
Imitation of foreign culture	70	35%
Unruly behavior	30	15%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 6 shows that 100 respondents believe that media technology makes the youths who are students have less time for their academic work. 70 (35%) respondents, on the other hand, said that the youths' usage of media technology makes them imitate the culture of Westerners, which varies from African culture. While the remaining 30 (15%) respondents viewed unruly behavior as one influence of media technology.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents on the negative effects of media technology on the lives of the youths.

Most effective solution	Frequency	Percentage
Proper orientation on media disadvantage	100	50%
Irrelevant sites should be blocked	30	15%
Seminars/workshops on media usage	70	35%
Total	200	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The above table shows that a large number of respondents, 100 (50%), advocated for proper orientation on media disadvantages given to the youths as the most effective solution to stopping the negative effects on the youths. The second group of respondents numbering 30 (15%) went for the blockage of irrelevant sites, while the third group supported the organization of seminars/workshops on media technology usage as the most effective means of mitigating its effects on the youths.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The data from the field presented useful insight into the effect of media technology on the behaviours of the youths in Agbani Community. The following are some of the major findings that emanated from the study.

The study showed the extent to which media technology is used by the youths in Agbani Community, which has been rated by the highest percentage (45%) as "very high," thus portraying Agbani Community as a place where media technology is very much patronized.

Again, the findings disclosed the factors responsible for the effect of media technology in the community. Here, respondents of 145(72.5%) viewed that improper orientation of the youths about media technology is influenced negatively by the use of it.

Concerning how media technology has influenced youth's behavior, 50% of the respondents said it makes the youth dedicate less time to academic work. Thus, rendering credence to Bowling (2009) , who is of the opinion that media technology makes the youths addicted to using it, and this more often lures one away from performing classroom and household chores, 35% of the respondents said that frequent media technology usage makes the youths imitate Western culture, which is different from African culture. 15% blamed the unruly behavior of the youths on media technology.

Proper orientation of the youths on media disadvantage was rated as the most effective solution to mitigating the effect of media technology on the youth's behavior. This was followed by the blockage of irrelevant sites and the organization of seminars/workshops on media usage.

CONCLUSION

The main focus of this study was to determine the effects of media technology on youths in Agbani Community. The study brings out the fact that the effects of media technology on the youths are real and are therefore matters of concern in Nigeria.

As a result of the above, the study concludes that less time for academic work, imitation of Western cultures, and unruly behavior on the part of the youths are directly related to media technology.

RECOMMENDATION

To solve the problem of media technology and its effects on the behaviours of youths in Agbani Community, these recommendations have been put forward.

- a. Proper orientation on media technology disadvantages: The youths should be given a sound orientation on the disadvantages of media technology if not properly used. This will help to reshape the behaviours of the youths of that community to a better standard.
- b. Irrelevant sites should be blocked: some of the new existing technologies carry sites that are harmful and detrimental to the well-being of the youths, instead of impacting them. For instance, there are sites on the internet exclusively for pornographic films. These types of sites should be blocked in order to reduce the moral decadence witnessed in the lives of youths in Agbani Community.
- c. Seminars and workshops on media technology: The government, schools, and well-to-do individuals should organize seminars or workshops on media technology and teach the youths how to use them properly.

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